

Tea Consumption Can Ascertain Employee Wellness: An Exploration

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ABSTRACT

The Tea Industry in India derives its importance by being one of the major foreign exchange earners and for playing a vital role towards employment generation as the industry is highly labor intensive. A healthy workplace means more than just warding off colds and the flu. It is more holistic and takes into consideration the physical, spiritual, environmental, intellectual, emotional, occupational and mental health of employees. This paper proposes the concept of customized consumption of tea to health condition of employees at workplace which is the need of the hour as health of employees are at stake now due to the enormous pressure and stress. The work life balance is of high care and concern as the basic need to work to earn money is to take care of our health and life but now we lose the health and wellbeing to work is something very alarming and requires high concern to take a call on it at the earliest. The HR department of every office makes sure on the comfort zone and level maintained at the workplace yet there are a number of complications occur due to mismanaged lifestyle and work life. Now, this papers calls attention on the concept of Tea Consumption aligned to their health condition for better wellness at the workplace which in return brings good working condition and accomplishment of needful tasks. Thus, this paper proposes the concept of Managed Tea Consumption, as given below.

Keywords: Tea, Employee Wellness, Work-life Balance, Health Rejuvenation

I. INTRODUCTION

The Tea Industry in India derives its importance by being one of the major foreign exchange earners and for playing a vital role towards employment generation as the industry is highly labor intensive. India is the second largest producer of tea in the world and contributes to around 30% of the global tea production. The market size of tea is estimated to be approx., 10,000 Crore with a penetration of more than 90% in the domestic market. With an export of approx. 210 million kg of tea, India stands as the fourth largest exporter of tea in the world with China ranking at the first position. The tea sector in the country is largely organized since 72% of the total area under tea cultivation and 74% of the total production comes from the organized sector. Tea in India is grown over an area of 600000 hectare (ha) which accounts for 16% of the total area under tea cultivation in the world. The Indian tea industry is having thousands of tea gardens spread across various states of India. In West Bengal and Assam there are around 8,500 tea estates, while in the southern states of Kerala, Karnataka and Tamil Nadu there are another 5,500 tea estates. Assam produces over half of India's tea and accounts for over 12% of the annual global tea yield, according to ASSOCHAM. Indian tea market is huge with large number of local and regional players. With the passage of time and due to change in the consumption pattern, there has been diversification and value addition in tea production.

In India, tea is consumed in two forms: packaged (branded) or loose. While a major share of the market is of loose tea suppliers, branded tea manufacturers are also fast increasing their market share. The demand for packet tea is driven by rising consumer incomes, quality of tea and product diversification with flavored tea production. The share of CTC tea constitutes 80% of the tea market followed by Orthodox Tea & Darjeeling Tea. Apart from them there are also a variety of flavored teas such as green tea, earl grey tea, jasmine tea, ginseng oolong, masala chai, green lemon tea, etc. CTC (cut, twist and curl) tea is the major contributor in the tea market segment but with the increasing consciousness on the health issues, green tea sales are picking up. Specialty tea market in India is growing at the rate of 25% annually. Tea production is expected to inch up marginally higher than last year in 2013-14 on account of better productivity from North India. India is the second largest producer of tea in the world with a 25% share of total production, but the country consumes 75-80% of its own production. Annual production of tea in 2013 stood at 1200 million kg, with North India accounting for 79% in total production and the rest coming from South India. Tea production in India in

2013 grew by 6.5% with a production of 1200 million kgs as compared to 1,126 million kgs in 2012. The production increase had little impact on exports as the majority of this tea was CTC grade and effectively all was consumed by the fast-growing domestic market.

II. HISTROY OF TEA CONSUMPTION

In one popular Chinese legend, Shennong, the legendary Emperor of China and inventor of agriculture and Chinese medicine was drinking a bowl of just boiled water due to a decree that his subjects must boil water before drinking it sometime around 2737 BC when a few leaves were blown from a nearby tree into his water, changing the color. The emperor took a sip of the brew and was pleasantly surprised by its flavor and restorative properties. A variant of the legend tells that the emperor tested the medical properties of various herbs on him, some of them poisonous, and found tea to work as an antidote. Shennong is also mentioned in Lu Yu's famous early work on the subject, *The Classic of Tea*. A similar Chinese legend goes that the god of agriculture would chew the leaves, stems, and roots of various plants to discover medicinal herbs. If he consumed a poisonous plant, he would chew tea leaves to counteract the poison. A rather gruesome legend dates back to the Tang Dynasty. In the legend, Bodhidharma, the founder of Chan Buddhism, accidentally fell asleep after meditating in front of a wall for nine years. He woke up in such disgust at his weakness that he cut off his own eyelids.

They fell to the ground and took root, growing into tea bushes. Sometimes, another version of the story is told with Gautama Buddha in place of Bodhidharma. Scholars however believe that tea drinking likely originated in the southwest of China, and that the Chinese words for tea themselves may have been originally derived from the Austro-Asiatic languages of the people who originally inhabited that area. Whether or not these legends have any basis in fact, tea has played a significant role in Asian culture for centuries as a staple beverage, a curative, and a status symbol. It is not surprising, therefore, that theories of its origin are often religious or royal in nature. The earliest record of tea in a more occidental writing is said to be found in the statement of an Arabian traveler, that after the year 879 the main sources of revenue in Canton were the duties on salt and tea. Marco Polo records the deposition of a Chinese minister of finance in 1285 for his arbitrary augmentation of the tea taxes.

The travelers Giovanni Batista Ramusio (1559), L. Almeida (1576), Maffei (1588), and Teixeira (1610) also mentioned tea. In 1557, Portugal established a trading port in Macau and word of the Chinese drink "chá" spread quickly, but there is no mention of them bringing any samples home. In the early 17th century, a ship of the Dutch East India Company brought the first green tea leaves to Amsterdam from China. Tea was known in France by 1636. It enjoyed a brief period of popularity in Paris around 1648. The history of tea in Russia can also be traced back to the seventeenth century. Tea was first offered by China as a gift to Czar Michael I in 1618. The Russian ambassador tried the drink; he did not care for it and rejected the offer, delaying tea's Russian introduction by fifty years. In 1689, tea was regularly imported from China to Russia via a caravan of hundreds of camels traveling the year-long journey, making it a precious commodity at the time. Tea was appearing in German apothecaries by 1657 but never gained much esteem except in coastal areas such as Ostfriesland. Tea first appeared publicly in England during the 1650s, where it was introduced through coffeehouses. From there it was introduced to British colonies in America and elsewhere.

III. NEED FOR HUMAN WELLNESS

A healthy workplace means more than just warding off colds and the flu. It is more holistic and takes into consideration the physical, spiritual, environmental, intellectual, emotional, occupational and mental health of employees. Wellness promotion doesn't just benefit the employee because an organization filled with healthy and fulfilled employees is a productive workplace that retains its employees. More and more organizations are creating Health and Welfare Committees who are responsible for recognizing health and safety concerns and identifying solutions. Chronic diseases such as depression and hypertension can lead to a decline in the overall health of employees in a workplace, contribute to an increase in health-related expenses for employers and employees, and lead to lower productivity and/or days of work missed. Many businesses have realized the benefits of health promotion, and to curb the costs of rising health care offer workplace health programs to their employees. Ideally, the office should be a place protecting the safety and well-being of employees while providing them with opportunities for better long-term health.

In a study published January 2014 in CDC's *Preventing Chronic Disease*, Bonauto and colleagues looked at data from 37,626 employees in Washington State and found that the overall incidence of obesity among workers was 24.6%. The authors also note that obesity rates varied by job type. For instance, only 11.6% of those in health-diagnosing occupations, for example doctors, dentists, and veterinarians, were obese. On the other hand, 38.6% of truck drivers, who spend most of their days sitting, were obese. The authors of this study acknowledge the importance of physical activities and their availability at the workplace in preventing obesity. Although chronic diseases like obesity are among the most common and costly of all health problems, adopting healthy lifestyles can help prevent them. A workplace health program aimed at keeping employees healthy is a key long-term human asset management strategy.

IV. MANAGED TEA CONSUMPTION

Tea, especially green tea, is often said to be good for your health. Tea contains substances linked to a lower risk for heart disease, cancer, and diabetes. But keep tea's healthy boost in perspective, says the September 2014 Harvard Men's Health Watch. "Tea consumption, especially green tea, may not be the magic bullet, but it can be incorporated in an overall healthy diet with whole grains, fish, fruits and vegetables, and less red and processed meat," says Qi Sun, assistant professor in the Department of Nutrition at the Harvard School of Public Health. The main health-promoting substances in tea are polyphenols, in particular catechins and epicatechins. Lab and animal studies say these molecules have anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. Harvard-led studies of large groups of people over time have found that tea or coffee drinkers are at lower risk for diabetes and possibly cardiovascular disease. Coffee also contains polyphenols. Now here's the key caveat: It remains unclear whether the tea itself is the cause of these benefits and, if so, how it works its magic.

The studies attempt to rule out the possibility that tea drinkers simply live healthier lifestyles, but it's difficult to be sure. That said, tea itself appears to have no harmful effects except for a case of the jitters if you drink too much caffeinated brew. It fits in perfectly well with a heart-healthy lifestyle. One important warning: A cup of tea contains only a couple calories. Processed, sugar-sweetened tea beverages are loaded with extra calories. "If there are any health benefits to green tea consumption, it's probably completely offset by adding sugar," Sun says. Tea has been linked to numerous health benefits, from a reduced risk of heart attacks and high blood pressure to potential protection against certain cancers. Now, a study suggests that the biological effects of the beverage may extend to the genetic level: Drinking tea might change how DNA is expressed, which could play a role in disease susceptibility and overall health. Behavior or environment can trigger chemical modifications in the body that affect which genes are turned on and off, the study of which is known as epigenetics.

In the new study, published in Human Molecular Genetics, tea drinking for women was associated with epigenetic changes in 28 different gene regions known to interact with cancer or estrogen metabolism. According to legend, the health effects of tea have been examined ever since the first infusions of *Camellia sinensis* about 4700 years ago in China. Emperor Shennong claimed in *The Divine Farmer's Herb-Root Classic* that *Camellia sinensis* infusions were useful for treating a variety of disease conditions. Historically as well as today, in regions without access to safe drinking water, the boiling of water to make tea has been effective in reducing waterborne diseases by destroying pathogenic microorganisms. Recently, concerns have been raised about the traditional method of over-boiling tea to produce a decoction, which may increase the amount of pesticides and other harmful contaminants released and consumed. Black tea has been studied extensively for its potential to lower the risk of human diseases, but none of this research is conclusive as of 2015.

V. HUMAN WELLNESS ATTAINED BY TEA CONSUMPTION

This paper proposes the concept of customized consumption of tea to health condition of employees at workplace which is the need of the hour as health of employees at stake now due to the enormous pressure and stress. The work life balance is of high care and concern as the basic need to work to earn money is to take care of our health and life but now we lose the health and wellbeing to work is something very alarming and requires high concern to take a call on it at the earliest. The HR department of every office makes sure on the comfort zone and level maintained at the workplace yet there are a number of complications occur due to mismanaged lifestyle and work life. Now, this papers calls attention on the concept of Tea Consumption aligned to their health condition for better wellness at the workplace which in return brings good working condition and accomplishment of needful tasks. Thus, this paper proposes the concept of Managed Tea Consumption, as given below.

S.NO.	GENERAL HEALTH ISSUES	MANAGED TEA CONSUMPTION	BENEFITS
1	GENERAL WEAKNESS	Sun Dried Orange Skin with Black Grapes or Raisins	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kills Germs & Bacteria • Natural Fragrance • Improves Digestion & Increases Appetite
2	COMMON COLD	Mint, Ginger, Black Pepper & Black Cardamom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anti Oxidant • Protects from Flu • Increases Immunity
3	ORDINARY FEVER	Black tea (More Water), Black Pepper, Cinnamon Stick, Dry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increases Immunity

		Ginger mixed with Honey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protects from Bacterial Infection • Increases Rejuvenation Features
4	DYSENTRY	Double Dose Black Tea simmers with reducing the content.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acts as Contraceptive Conjunction Agent • Improves Health of Digestive System and Retains Energy • Increases Rejuvenation Features
5	ANAEMIA & LOW IMMUNITY	Ice Tea, Pomegranate Extract mixed with Beetroot Extract with Lemon & Honey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contains Natural Iron & Folic Acids • Good Sources of Vitamins & Calcium and thins the Blood and improves the Iron Content for the Body
6	STOMACH ULCER	Tea with Less Decoction (Light), Fresh Yogurt, Sugar, Brewed Light Tea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Natural Pro Biotic Content • Helps for Healthier Digestive System • Provides instant Minerals, Potassium, Calcium Etc.,
7	HEAD ACHE	EP: Brewed Hot Tea boiled with Eucalyptus Leaves or Oil (Stream Inhaling) IP: Brewed Hot Tea boiled with Coriander Leaves with few Mint Leave	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cures Migraine Head Ache • Eucalyptus Leaves sustains properties like Anti Inflammatory & Anti Spasmodic & Decongestant Agent which releases essential oil content sustaining Distinctive Taste & Fragrance
8	OBESITY	Black Tea with Lemon Juice with Green Peppercorn Extract	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Green Peppercorn Extract naturally a fat burner helps to manage the Hydrochloric Acid level in the stomach • Black Tea & Lemon Juice acts as a Diuretic Agent & Helps to have the reduced Appetite
9	DEHYDRATION	Reduced Green Tea with Electrolyte (Natural Electrolyte alike Tender Coconut Water, Aloe vera Juice, Palm Fruit Pulp)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increases the Water Content and balances it with Amino acid • Natural Electrolyte supplies Instant Required Micro Nutrients to the Blood Vessels & Improves the Energy level in the Body • Jagerry & Palm Candy contains Natural Source of Iron which provides instant energy to the body.
10	DIABETICS & BLOOD PRESSURE	Brewed Green Tea Extract along with Rose Mary and Thyme Leaves Crushed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rose Mary contains rich amino acids and is anti fungal and anti bacterial agents • RM also fights against cancer due to a substance called Cineol • It also keeps Diabetic Away • Thyme has Thymol which balances Hormone secretion

SUGGESTIONS

This paper proposes the below mentioned suggestions for better initiatives by the HR department for the wellness of the employees at the workplace customized based on the health condition of employees that increases the compatibility of tea consumption, ascertained wellness and accomplishments of work assignments, with reference to the above given tabulation. Such suggestions are as below given:

- HR department of companies sustaining large number of employees can hire a Dietician or a Health Manager to take care on the physical and mental issues of the employees at the workplace.
- The HR department can undertake an initiative to maintain a separate file on every individual on concern to their health condition and also periodically update it as such the HR office of the company is well aware on every employee's physical & mental condition.
- Based on the above mentioned Health Record of each employee, the office can offer opportunity for Managed Tea Consumption based on their physical and mental condition as given above in this paper.
- The office canteen can compose a TEA BAR to offer customized TEA to employees in their tea time aligned to their physical and mental condition as given in the table above.
- The Mocktail Tea Bar can ascertain the wellness of the employees on daily basis aligned to the condition of their physical and mental states to ascertain their wellbeing at workplace in a way that their productivity is maintained to accomplish the needful job.
- By initiating these types of wellness initiatives for the employees the employee's trust on the employer increases and loyalty of the employees on their office and their commitment to accomplish the tasks assigned increases which in return gains the better working atmosphere.
- By these initiatives it's not alone the employee's professional endeavors are taken care but also their personal private life too is done to ascertain happy healthy living. Managed Tea Consumption directly ascertains physical wellness but indirectly also ascertains the mental wellbeing of employees.

CONCLUSION

The world's most popular drink, next to water—and it's steeped in health benefits. Tea is a delicious beverage that can cool you down in the hot summer months and warm you up in the winter. Many different types of tea, such as white tea, green tea, yellow tea, black tea, oolong tea and pu-erh tea, all sustains significant benefits for human wellbeing in a number of ways. The type of tea produced from this plant depends entirely on the way the leaves are processed after harvesting. Different processing methods give tea leaves from the same plant their own distinct color and flavor. Thus this paper has threw light on Managed Tea Consumption which ascertains customized employee's health conditions for better work-life they can lead which is beneficial to both the ends at employees as well as at employers. Further, this paper opens way for further researches to focus upon special tea sustains ingredients that stimulate the capabilities which lack by a range of employees who can be well prescribed and managed for those tea consumption for better capability ascertaining in employees and effective work accomplishments for the employers.

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